

A methodology to assess the mechanical behavior of plant fibers - Application to flax fiber rovings under tensile loading

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Abstract

In this work we investigate the tensile behavior of flax fiber rovings. The usual methods applied to synthetic fibers are indeed unsuitable for plant fibers such as flax. Acoustic emission is correlated with the mechanical loading curve to identify the different damage mechanisms of the roving: breaks of unit fibers, delamination in fiber bundles and their breaks. From the mechanical parameters or data acoustic emission analysis of the growth of the damage according to the deformation shows the same trend. These results can be useful to assess qualitatively and quantitatively the effects of mechanical (pulping, for example), physicochemical or thermal treatments on the properties of vegetable fibers.

1. Introduction

In textile plants bark contiguous cells specialize each in ultimate fiber and the organization of these fiber bundles provides support for the plant. Unless applying a specific mechanical and/or chemical treatment to obtain ultimate fibers, they are in the form of bundles from the defibering step to the composite fabrication step.

The different defibering methods implemented (retting, scutching and hackling) affect the smoothness, the state of the surface and the mechanical properties of the fibers, and it is necessary to assess their impact. So far, the mechanical properties of flax fibers are mostly measured on the individual fibers to estimate the influence of the variety (Thuault, 2011), thermal treatment (Destaing, 2012), mechanical pulping treatment (Barbulée, 2011) or to correlate these properties to those of the composite (Coroller, 2013).

Indeed the tests on ultimate fibers allow the estimation of the distribution of mechanical properties, but they cannot provide information on the cohesion of the bundle, which is however an important factor in understanding the mechanical behavior of fiber bundles and rovings. In fact, the morphology and the cohesion of fiber bundles are closely related to the variety and growing conditions. Pectic cements that hold the fiber bundles have low mechanical properties because pectins are very sensitive to hydrothermal conditions (Fraeye, 2007). Then, the selection of ultimate fibers by manual extraction false results because the process eliminates the weakest and damages the most resistant. Furthermore, because defects are rather concentrated in specific areas in the stem (leaves settlements; for example), testing ultimate fibers underestimates the presence of such defects. On the other hand, many challenges remain regarding the mechanical characterization of ultimate fibers. Uncertainties related to the knowledge of the cross-section area of the fiber at the location of failure (the presence of the lumen, the non-circularity of the fiber section, cross-section area change along the fiber) impacts the estimates of the Young's modulus and the tensile strength (Charlet, 2008). Furthermore, the standardized tensile test with a gauge length of 10 mm causes a problem for the representativeness of the results.

On the contrary, in the fiber bundle, the cooperative effect of ultimate fibers allow reducing the dispersion of the measured mechanical properties, revealing better the defects within the fiber and having a more realistic insight on the mechanical properties of the basic entity that constitutes the reinforcement used in the composite.

In view of these points, we attempted to develop a reliable methodology for the mechanical characterization of plant fibers at the scale of the roving. The roving is a collection of fiber bundles more or less bound by bark residues or other tissues. By testing a roving, we can measure its properties without disturbing its integrity or modifying its structure and therefore its properties. Then it may be possible to assess the properties of the constitutive fiber bundles and thereby the properties of the ultimate fibers.

Data obtained on the roving can be used for understanding the deformation mechanisms of reinforcing fibers when shaping technical parts (Boisse, 2011; Ouagne, 2013). They are also needed for modeling the mechanical behavior of the composite by homogenization approaches.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Flax fiber – different entities

The bundles of fibers are from the same stem that has undergone moderate scutching characterized by a feeding rate of 30 m/min, a grinding intensity of 5 bars and a threshing speed of 62 laps/min (Vandecandelaere Scutching Company, Depestele Group in Bourguébus, France). The flax stems are the Melina strain that was grown in 2012 in the plain of Caen (France). Schematic views of the different arrangements of flax fibers evoked in this study are shown in figure 1.

Fig. 1: Different arrangements of the flax fibers in the roving

2.2. Sample preparation

Flax fibers possess high axial mechanical properties but significantly lower values in the radial directions (Bourmaud, 2011). Thus, fitting a fiber bundle to the jaw for the tensile test is tricky: on the one hand it must be maintained in the jaw without crushing; on the other one must ensure its perfect alignment with the axis of traction to avoid inadvertent damage to the vicinity of the clamping area. In addition, the fiber bundles must remain parallel to each other in the roving (a), all fiber bundles must be loaded at the same time from the beginning of the test (b), the parasitic friction between the fibers should be minimized (c), two independent fiber bundles should break apart (d). To this end, one must align the fiber bundles and spread

up the roving without altering the links between the fiber bundles. We have designed and built a device that can meet these technical rules. The organization of the roving so obtained is saved by molding both ends in steel shells using a resin, which sets the gauge length of the test piece.

2.3. Sample testing

These specimens are loaded on a universal mechanical testing machine (INSTRON type, 1185 series) ensuring a uniform clamping in the jaws and a perfect alignment. The uniaxial tensile tests are conducted at a deformation controlled rate of 1% /min, using a 2 kN capacity load cell.

Given the sensitivity of plant fibers to hydrothermal conditions, the tests are conducted in a climatic chamber at 25 ° C and 50% RH. Prior to the tests, the samples had been loaded for 3 hours to ensure the stabilization of the water content of the fiber.

In order to study the damage to the roving, an acoustic emission device (MISTRAS type) was used. It includes a PCI-2 data acquisition system, two PICO piezoelectric sensors for the location of damaging sources. The main parameters set for the acquisition of acoustic emission are a detection threshold of 40 dB and a gain of 40 dB. The acoustic emission was recorded by setting the hit end determination time HDT = 800 μ s, the reset time HLT = 1000 μ s and the maximum burst determination time PDT = 200 μ s.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Validation of the test device

a. Choice of the resin and precautions for making the samples

The nature of the resin for making the samples is important because we must ensure that it does not induce premature aging, deterioration or breakage of the fibers in the jaws. The choice fell on a chemically stable and neutral pH epoxy resin. The chosen fabrication technique avoids the infiltration of the resin in the calibrated zone area of the roving, which would reduce the gauge length.

b. Alignment and iso-tension of the fiber bundles within the roving

To assess the fair alignment of the loading device and the iso-tension of the fiber bundles in the roving, we compared the deformation necessary to obtain a linear behavior of the roving (ϵ_l) to the deformation at rupture of the first fiber bundle (ϵ_{bf}). To this end, we have identified the linear elastic behavior domain on the loading curve (Fig. 2) and have drawn the line of greatest slope (O'z) that meets the horizontal axis of deformation at point O'. This point is identified at the origin of the loading curve that would be obtained if the loading assembly had infinite stiffness and all fiber bundles were equally strained. The fact that all the fiber bundles are not equally strained explains why the experimental loading curve intersects the (O'z) line at the abscissa R (ϵ_l). The ratio (ϵ_l/ϵ_{fb}) is an indicator of the iso-tension of the fiber bundles at the beginning of the test, the iso-tension is the more effective this ratio is the lower. For tests on 10 flax rovings with a gauge length of 10 cm, the average ratio is 18 %.

Fig. 2: Evaluation of the iso-tension of the fiber bundles

c. Reliability of strain measurements

As flax fibers are not continuous along the gauge length, we could use no mechanical extensometer for strain measurements as is customary with synthetic fibers (R'mili and Murat, 1997). The relative elongation of the fiber bundles between two specific points taken in the calibrated zone was measured under an optical microscope for different load levels and compared to the expected nominal strain. For a nominal strain of 0.8%, that measured on the roving is 0.77%. Moreover, a numerical simulation was made under ANSYS for estimating the displacement in the matrix parallel to the axis of a flax fiber embedded in the resin and subjected to a tensile stress of 800 MPa (its mean ultimate stress). The maximum displacement obtained is 30 μm . These results indicate that the developed loading set does not significantly disturb the deformation of the roving.

3.2. Identification of several damaging mechanisms

The loading curve of a roving consisting of several fiber bundles (Fig. 2) shows a first domain corresponding to the linear elastic behavior, followed by a non-linear zone in which acoustic emission appears. The end of this second area is marked by the breakdown of the first fiber bundle and is manifested by a more or less pronounced drop in load. Further increase in strain results in a recovery of the load until the failure of another fiber bundle. The sequence of these events leads to the typical saw-tooth shape of the load-deformation curve. Analysis of successive losses of stiffness of the roving and the associated variations in elastic energy can be correlated with the acoustic analysis (duration, energy and amplitude of the hits) to identify the different damage mechanisms (first column in Table 1). For example, the representation of the hit duration versus the rigidity of the roving (Fig. 3) allows identifying three families of damage mechanisms shown in the last column in Table 1. These three main features are also revealed when the variation in rigidity of the roving is expressed as a function of hits energy (Fig. 4). The main mechanisms identified are shown in Table 1 and specified in terms of their mechanical and acoustic signatures. Figure 5 shows the correlation between the identified mechanisms and the load-deformation curve.

Fig. 3: Hit duration as a function of the reduction in roving rigidity

Fig. 4: Reduction in the roving rigidity as a function of hit absolute energy

Fig. 5: Damage mechanisms identified on the loading curve

Table 1: Different damage mechanisms identified by the correlation of the loading curve with the acoustic emission (N/% means newton per percentage of deformation)

Damage mechanisms	Analysis of the loading curve		Analysis of the acoustic emission signals			Different families of damaging mechanism
	Reduction in the roving rigidity (N/%)	Elastic energy variation	Hit duration (μ s)	Hit energy (10^9 ato J)	Amplitude (dB)	
Friction among ultimate fibers or bundles	Non detectable	Non detectable		Low energy	Low	#1
Rupture of ultimate fibers	Very low	Non detectable		Low	Medium	
Delamination among or within bundles	< 80	Low	> 1500	< 5	< 80	#2
Rupture of bundles with load transfer onto neighbouring bundles	< 80	Low/Medium	> 1500	> 5	> 80	
Catastrophic rupture of the bundle	> 80	High	> 1500	> 5	80-100	#3

3.3. Analyses of damage accumulation in the roving

The results presented above indicate that various mechanical and acoustic parameters can be used to describe the evolution of the damage to the roving. In the following we analyze the damage through the variations of three mechanical parameters and an acoustic parameter.

a. Number of broken bundles

The growth rate of broken fiber bundles as the deformation raises can be considered as an indicator of damage to the roving. In this analysis, an equal importance is given to each fiber bundle, regardless the number of ultimate fibers or sub-bundles. This trend is illustrated in figure 6.

b. Cumulative sum of the reductions of the fiber bundles rigidity

Loss of rigidity of the roving is expressed by the ratio of the load reduction (upon rupture of a fiber or bundle) to deformation at that moment. This analysis takes implicitly into account the size of each fiber bundle. The cumulative sum of the losses of rigidity is shown in figure 6 as a function of the deformation.

Fig. 6: Representation of the damage as the cumulative sum of: the released elastic energy or the acoustic energy as function of the deformation.

c. Cumulative sum of released elastic energy

When a micro-rupture occurs within the roving (gauge length l_0) for a deformation ε with an associated load reduction ΔP , the released elastic energy is:

$$\frac{(\Delta P \cdot \varepsilon \cdot l_0)}{2} \quad (1)$$

The statistical weight of this damage should not depend on the strain ε at which it occurs. If one wants to implement a statistical analysis, the released elastic energy must be multiplied by a term $1/(\varepsilon \cdot l_0)^2$:

$$\frac{\Delta P}{(2 \cdot \varepsilon \cdot l_0)} \quad (2)$$

This method of estimating the damage takes into account all energy dispersive mechanisms. The plot of the values calculated with the expression (2) as a function of the deformation of the roving is shown in figure 7.

d. Cumulative sum of acoustic energy

The energy associated to an acoustic event is proportional to the square of its amplitude. Thus, the acoustic energy collected during the test includes the contributions of all the damaging phenomena listed in Table 1. The accumulated sum of acoustic energy is shown in figure 7, as a function of the deformation of the roving.

Fig. 7: Representation of the damage estimated by: the rate of fiber bundles rupture or the cumulated sum of the reductions of the roving rigidity as function of the deformation.

4. Conclusion

A methodology was developed for tensile testing plant fiber roving, including the fabrication of a set allowing the iso-tension of the fiber bundles constitutive of the roving and the validation of a dedicated clamping device. The relevance of this test method was evaluated by identifying different damaging mechanisms of flax fiber roving, and by the ability to determine the deformation associated to the failure of each fiber bundle within the roving. The damage growth was studied as a function of deformation by analyzing the force-deformation curves or the acoustic emission data. The comparison among these different methods shows a very good correlation between the two sets of results.

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